

MORPHOLOGY ANALYSIS AND SHAPE OPTIMAL OF CFRTP-SMC BASED ON MONTE- CARLO SIMULATION

R. Xu, Y. Wan and J. Takahashi
Department of Systems Innovation
The University of Tokyo

No. 1266

TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS (ICCM23)
30 JULY ~ 4 AUGUST
Belfast, United Kingdom

Contents

- Introduction
- Monte Carlo Simulation Model
- Result Analysis and Comparison
- Summary and Future Plan

Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have high specific strength and stiffness, which is used in a wide range of applications such as aircraft, automobile and sports gear.

From the viewpoint of application to mass-produced vehicles, there are high expectations for carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic(CFRTP).

BMW i3^[2]

Lamborghini^[3]

Comparison

This research focused on **CFRTP-SMC** (Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics sheet molding compound). This material has many advantages such as higher fiber volume fraction than injection molded materials, more suitable in complex Design than continuous laminates material and in-plane isotropic.

Type of composite system	Injection molded 			
Fiber continuity	Discontinuous	Discontinuous	Discontinuous	Continuous
Fiber volume fraction V_f	<5%	Around 10 to 30%	$\geq 50\%$	$\geq 50\%$
Fiber Length	Around 1 mm or less	Several millimeters	Around 10 to 100 millimeters	Continuous
Complex Design	Suitable	Possible	Suitable	Difficult
Anisotropy	Process dependent	In-plane isotropic Out-of-plane orthotropic	In-plane isotropic Out-of-plane orthotropic	Designable

[4] Yamashita S, Hashimoto K; Sukanuma H; Takahashi J Experimental characterization of the tensile failure mode of ultra thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 35 , 18, pp.1342-1352, (2016)

Research purpose

Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Vf & mechanical properties • Complex shape design in manufacturing
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex tape distribution • Difficulty in prediction of mechanical properties

[5] Yamashita S, Hashimoto K; Sukanuma H; Takahashi J Experimental characterization of the tensile failure mode of ultra thin chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 35 , 18, pp.1342-1352, (2016)

Monte Carlo Simulation

Advantages:

- Probability Distribution
- Sensitivity Analysis
- Parallelizability

Monte-Carlo simulation process

The method involves generating a large number of random samples or scenarios from inputs or parameters that describe inner structure of CFRTP-SMC material

Contents

- Introduction
- Monte Carlo Simulation Model
- Result Analysis and Comparison
- Summary and Future Plan

SMC Model Program Design

Class Definition - Tape

Class Definition - Layer & Specimen

Layer - 2D Array

Number of Width Unit

n_{layer} =

Number of Length Unit

$col = int\left(\frac{l_{specimen}}{l_{unit}}\right)$ $row = int\left(\frac{w_{specimen}}{l_{unit}}\right)$

Specimen - 3D Array

$n_{layer} = ceil\left(\frac{t_{specimen}}{t_{tape}}\right)$

Tape Distribution

Tape Overlapped in Multiple Layers

Calculate tape overlapped in three or more layers

Three Tapes Overlapped

Tape Cross Two Layers

Tape Cross Multiple Layers

Based on Sinking Algorithm

(Operated by **Recursive Algorithm** & Generated by **Sweep Line Algorithm**)

Overlap Area Calculation

Layer 20 Visualization

Layer 21 Visualization

← Adjacent Two Layers →

Calculate Overlap Area

Overlap Area Visualization

Following from overlap matrix:

- Overlap Area Position
- Each Area Value
- Overlap Area Distribution

Overlap Layers Distribution

Overlap Area Ratio in mass simulation (n=50)

Contents

- Introduction
- Monte Carlo Simulation Model
- Result Analysis and Comparison
- Summary and Future Plan

Result Comparison – Overlap in Different Length

Overlap Area Histogram with Normal Curve
(n=50 length=12mm, 18mm, 24mm, 30mm width=5mm)

Variance increase with
tape length increasing.

Result Comparison – Overlap in Different Length

Overlap Area Distribution with Tape Length

Area ≈ 20, Frequency ≈ 200

Frequency of 2nd Peak increases with tape length increasing.

Number of overlap (area ≥ 20) is increasing

Result Comparison – Overlap in Different Width

Overlap Area Distribution with Tape Width

Overlap Area Calculation Result

Besides of the peak around 0, which is normal, there is also a peak around area of 25 mm^2 . This area is close of the square area of 5 mm , which is the width of tape. Therefore, we assume the frequency of this peak (y-axis) is determined by the **length of tape**.

Overlap Area Calculation Result

With tape length increasement, the **sum** of overlap area increase, which is majorly contributed by the second peak.

Compared to experiment data along with our simulation data, we assumed that the most optimized tape length-width tends to be around **6 (30mm / 5mm)**.

CF/PA6 UD sheet (Fukui prefecture) ³⁾
 - Vf: 54%
 - Tape Width: 5mm
 - Tape Thickness: 0.044mm

However

Longer tape length problem:
 - Lower Vf rate
 - High variance

Contents

- Introduction
- Monte Carlo Simulation Model
- Result Analysis and Comparison
- Summary and Future Plan

Conclusion

Summary:

- ✓ Monte Carlo Simulation Model for CFRTP-SMC.
- ✓ Analysis of the distribution of SMC tape and overlap.
- ✓ Best tape length-width ratio.

Future Task:

- a. Tensile strength prediction and comparison with different tape shapes.
- b. More experiments for verification and optimization.

Presentations from Takahashi-Wan lab

Name	Date	Venue	Room	Title
Zhiyu WANG	Mon	Process modelling - S1	Studio	A state-based peridynamic model for progressive damage analysis of CFRTP-SMC base
Peng XUE	Mon	Structural analysis and optimization - S2	3B	Optimization of floating vertical axis wind turbine structures using recycled carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic
Xiaohang TONG	Tue	Mechanics of composites - S2	3A	The influence of tape geometry on the mechanical performance of bolted CFRTP-SMC joints
Zihao ZHAO	Tue	Liquid composites moulding - S2	2A	Simulation of fiber orientation during compression molding process of CFRTP-SMC
▶ Ruo Chen XU	Wed	Multiscale modelling - S5	Studio	Morphology analysis and shape optimal of CFRTP-SMC based on Monte-Carlo simulation
Qian GAO	Wed	Recycling and sustainability - S3	1B	Prediction of strength and its variation of carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics using Monte-Carlo method
Weizhao HUANG	Thu	Structural health monitoring - S1	Arc	Inversing spatial modulus distribution of cfrtp by a vibrational method and its hydrothermal aging application

Thank you for your attention!

Acknowledgement:

The authors would like to express sincere thanks to Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture for supplying the specially developed CFRTP-SMC material and to the members who have provided valuable information and useful discussions.